

Supplementary material 1: Tables of evidence for framework

Table S1. Studies relating to contexts, mechanisms and outcomes for diagnosis of a rare disease

Label (C=Context; M=Mechanism; O=Outcome)	Mechanism/Outcome	Evidence shared across RD community	Evidence within specific groups in RD community (PROGRESS+)					
			Place of residence	Race/ethnicity	Gender	SES	Age	Disability
<i>C1: Health policy, resourcing and organisation (wider context)</i>								
M1	Lack of care co-ordination	Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Hagena 2024 ²	-	-	-	-	Bell 2021 ³	-
<i>C2: Primary care</i>								
M2	Lack of knowledge	Bennett 2021 ⁴ ; Daker-White 2013 ⁵ ; Flaherty 2024 ⁶ ; Limb 2010 ⁷ ; Muir 2016 ⁸ ; Pavey 2013 ⁹	-	-	-	-	Simpson 2018 ¹⁰	Shah 2014 ¹¹
M3	Dismissive attitudes	Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Limb 2010 ⁷ ; O'Brien 2011 ¹² ; Pavey 2013 ⁹ ; Muir 2016 ⁸	-	Franklish 2022 ¹	Bell 2021 ³ ; Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Gilfillan 2024 ¹³	-	Bell 2021 ³ ; Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Simpson 2018 ¹⁰	-
O1	No/misdiagnosis	Bell 2021 ³ ; Dake-White 2013 ⁵ ; Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Husson 2019 ¹⁴ ; McDonald 2019 ¹⁵ ; Morgan 2021 ¹⁶ ; Muir 2016 ⁸ ; Sharma 2020 ¹⁷	-	-	-	-	Bell 2021 ³ ; McDonald 2019 ¹⁵	-
O2	Delayed diagnosis	Combs 2013 ¹⁸ ; Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Genetic Alliance UK ¹⁹ ; Hay 2021 ²⁰ ; Husson 2019 ¹⁴ ; O'Brien 2011 ¹²	-	-	-	-	Genetic Alliance UK ¹⁹	Shah 2014 ¹¹

C3: Secondary care (general hospital)								
M4	Lack of knowledge	Bennett 2021 ⁴ ; Daker-White 2013 ⁵ ; Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Muir 2016 ⁸ ; Twigg 2021 ²¹	-	-	-	-	-	-
M5	Dismissive attitudes	Bell 2021 ³	-	-	-	-	Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Bell 2021 ³	Griffith 2011 ²³
M6	Wrong specialist	Husson 2019 ¹⁴ ; Morgan 2021 ¹⁶	-	-	-	-	-	-
M7	Accessibility	Muir 2016 ⁸	-	-	-	-	-	-
O3	No/misdiagnosis	Muir 2016 ⁸ ; Twigg 2021 ²¹	-	-	-	-	-	-
O4	Delayed diagnosis	Husson 2019 ¹⁴	-	-	-	-	-	-
C4: Mental health services								
M8	Accessibility	Franklish 2022 ¹	-	-	-	-	-	-
C5: Genetic services								
M9	Accessibility	Genetic Alliance 2023 ¹⁹	Peter 2024 ²⁴	-	-	Peter 2024 ²⁴	-	-
M10	Limited data sets	Church Smith n.d. ²⁵ ; Oerton 2011 ²⁶ ; Wright 2022 ²⁷	-	Church Smith n.d. ²⁵ ; Oerton 2011 ²⁶ ; Wright 2022 ²⁷	-	-	-	-
O5	No diagnosis	Church Smith n.d. ²⁵ ; Oerton 2011 ²⁶ ; Wright 2022 ²⁷	-	Church Smith n.d. ²⁵ ; Oerton 2011 ²⁶ ; Wright 2022 ²⁷	-	-	-	-
C6: Specialist services								
M11	Wrong specialist	Muir 2016 ⁸	-	-	-	-	-	-
M12	Accessibility	Franklish 2022 ¹ ; O'Brien 2023 ²⁸	Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Peter 2024 ²⁴	-	-	Bell 2021 ³ ; Franklish 2022 ¹ ; O'Brien 2011 ¹² ; Pavey	-	-

						2013 ⁹ ; Peter 2024 ²⁴		
O6	Variable care standards (within RD community and between RD/general population)	Franklish 2022 ¹ ; O'Brien 2023 ²⁸	Franklish 2022 ¹ Peter 2024 ²⁴	-	-	Bell 2021 ³ ; Franklish 2022 ¹ ; O'Brien 2011 ¹² ; Pavey 2013 ⁹ ; Peter 2024 ²⁴	-	-
C7: RD diagnosis								
M13	Lack of information	Costa 2022 ²⁹ ; Crowe 2019 ³⁰ ; Hassall 2022 ³¹ ; O'Brien 2023 ²⁸	-	-	-	-	-	-
O7	Patient satisfaction	O'Brien 2023 ²⁸	-	-	-	-	-	-
O8	Delayed diagnosis	Akanuwe 2020 ³² ; Al-Attar 2018 ³³ ; Bell 2021 ³ ; Combs 2013 ¹⁸ ; Flaherty 2013 ⁶ ; Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Genetic Alliance 2023 ¹⁹ ; Limb 2010 ⁷ ; Muir 2016 ⁸ ; O'Brien 2023 ²⁸	-	-	Song 2024 ³⁴ ; Sanigorska 2022 ^{22*}	Bell 2021 ³ ; Franklish 2022 ¹ ; O'Brien 2011 ¹² ; Pavey 2013 ⁹ ; Peter 2024 ²⁴	Genetic Alliance 2023 ¹⁹ ; Song 2024 ³⁴	-
C8: SWAN diagnosis (see Table S2)								

Abbreviations: RD=rare disease; SES=socioeconomic status; SWAN=syndrome without a name

Table S2. Studies relating to contexts, mechanisms and outcomes for accessing health services with a rare disease

Label (C=Context; M=Mechanism; O=Outcome)	Type of inequity	Evidence shared across RD community	Evidence within specific groups in RD community (PROGRESS)					
			Place of residence	Race/ethnicity	Gender	SES	Age	Disability
C7: Rare disease diagnosis (see Table S1)								
C8: SWAN diagnosis								
M14	Accessibility	Aldiss 2021 ³⁵	-	Church Smith n.d. ²⁵ ; Oerton	-	-	Aldiss 2021 ³⁵	-

				2011 ²⁶ ; Wright 2022 ²⁷				
<i>C9: Health policy, resourcing and organisation</i>								
M15	Lack of care co-ordination	Aldiss 2021 ³⁵ ; Aljuburi 2012 ³⁶ ; Bell 2021 ³ ; Cassidy 2023 ³⁷ ; Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Genetic Alliance UK 2023 ¹⁹ ; Grose 2014 ³⁸ ; Harris 2018 ³⁹ ; Husson 2019 ¹⁴ ; Limb 2010 ⁷ ; Morris 2022 ⁴⁰ ; Multiple System Atrophy 2022 ⁴¹ ; Muir 2016 ⁸ ; Pinto 2021 ⁴² ; Spencer-Tansley 2018 ⁴³ ; Watson 2023 ⁴⁴	-	-	-	-	Aldiss 2021 ³⁵ ; Bell 2021 ³ ; Genetic Alliance UK 2023 ¹⁹ ; Haig-Ferguson ⁴⁵ ; Limb 2010 ⁷ ; Muir 2016 ⁸ ; Spencer Tansley 2018 ⁴³	-
<i>C10: Social care</i>								
M16	Lack of knowledge	Griffith 2011 ²³ ; O'Brien 2012 ⁴⁶ ; O'Brien 2011 ⁴⁷ ; Skirton 2010 ⁴⁸	-	-	-	-	-	-
M17	Dismissive attitudes	Franklish 2022 ¹	-	-	-	-	-	-
M18	Accessibility	Cohen 2017 ⁴⁹ ; Crowe 2019 ³⁰ ; McDonald 2019 ¹⁵	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>C11: Emergency services</i>								
M19	Lack of knowledge	Chakravorty 2018 ⁵⁰	-	-	-	-	-	-
M20	Dismissive attitudes	Renedo 2019 ⁵¹	-	Renedo 2019 ⁵¹	-	-	Renedo 2019 ⁵¹	-
O9	Service avoidance	Chakravorty 2018 ⁵⁰ ; Renedo 2019 ⁵¹	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>C12: Primary dental care</i>								
M21	Lack of knowledge	Kalsi 2012 ⁵²	-	-	-	-	-	-

M22	Accessibility	Booth 2023 ⁵³ ; Kalsi 2012 ⁵²	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>C13: Primary care (GP surgery)</i>								
M23	Lack of knowledge	Cassidy 2023 ³⁷ ; Daker-White 2013 ⁵ ; Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Vallortigara 2023 ⁵⁴ ; Wray 2021 ⁵⁵	-	-	-	-	Wray 2021 ⁵⁵	-
M24	Dismissive attitudes	Dures 2011 ⁵⁶ ; Franklish 2022 ¹	-	-	Whitaker 2021 ⁵⁷	-	-	-
M25	Lack of information	Aldiss 2021 ³⁵ ; Cassidy ³⁷ ; Neelamekam 2017 ⁵⁸ ; O'Brien 2012 ⁴⁶	-	-	Taylor 2014 ⁵⁹	-	Aldiss 2021 ³⁵	-
O10	Not listened to	Franklish 2022 ¹	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>C14: Secondary care (hospital)</i>								
M26	Lack of knowledge	Aubeeluck 2012 ⁶⁰ ; Bell 2021 ³ ; Bennett 2021 ⁴ ; Berghs 2022 ⁶¹ ; Cassidy 2023 ³⁷ ; Cunniff 2015 ⁶² ; Griffith 2011 ²³ ; Husson 2019 ¹⁴ ; Khair 2019 ⁶³ ; McMullan 2022 ⁶⁴ ; Morgan 2021 ¹⁶ ; Neelamekam 2017 ⁵⁸ ; O'Brien 2015 ⁶⁵ ; Simpson 2018 ¹⁰ ; Skirton 2010 ⁴⁸ ; Spencer-Tansley 2018 ⁴³	-	-	-	-	-	-
M27	Lack of information	Chakravorty 2018 ⁵⁰ ; Fixter 2017 ⁶⁶ ; O'Brien 2012 ⁴⁶ ; Pavey 2013 ⁹	-	-	-	-	Aldiss 2021 ³⁵	-
M28	Dismissive attitudes	Dures 2011 ⁵⁶ ; Miles 2019 ⁶⁷ ; Vasilica 2021 ⁶⁸	-	-	-	-	-	-
M29	Accessibility	Aldiss 2021 ³⁵ ; Daker-White 2013 ⁵	-	-	-	Bell 2021 ³ ; Morris 2022 ⁴⁰ ;	-	O'Brien 2015 ⁶⁵ ; Multiple System

						Khair 2019 ⁶³ ; Skirton 2010 ⁴⁸		Atrophy Trust 2022 ⁴¹
O11	Variable care standards (within RD community and between RD/general population)	Aldiss 2021 ³⁵ ; Daker-White 2013 ⁵ ; Muir 2016 ⁸	-	-	-	Bell 2021 ³ ; Morris 2022 ⁴⁰ ; Khair 2019 ⁶³ ; Skirton 2010 ⁴⁸	-	O'Brien 2015 ⁶⁵ ; Multiple System Atrophy Trust, 2022 ⁴¹
O12	Not listened to	Berghs 2024 ⁶⁹ ; Miles 2019 ⁶⁷ ; Morgan 2021 ¹⁶ ; Neelamekam 2017 ⁵⁸ ; Vasilica 2021 ⁶⁸	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>C15: Mental health services</i>								
M30	Accessibility	Cassidy 2023 ³⁷ ; Chakravorty 2018 ⁵⁰ ; Multiple System Atrophy Trust 2019 ⁷⁰ ; Multiple System Atrophy Trust ⁴¹ ; O'Brien 2012 ⁷¹ ; Trimmer 2024 ⁷² ; Limb 2010 ⁷	-	-	-	-	-	-
M31	Dismissive attitudes	Bennett 2021 ⁴ ; Berghs 2024 ⁶⁹ ; Berghs 2022 ⁶¹ ; Dures 2011 ⁵⁶ ; Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Whitehead 2012 ⁷³ ; Multiple System Atrophy Trust 2022 ⁴¹	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>C16: Maternity care</i>								
M32	Lack of knowledge	Anderson 2021 ^{74*}	-	-	Anderson 2021 ^{74*} ; Rance 2019 ⁷⁵	-	-	-
<i>C17: Specialist services</i>								
M33	Accessibility	Franklish 2022 ¹ ; Morris 2022 ⁴⁰ ; Morris 2023 ⁷⁶ ;	Aldiss 2021 ³⁵ ; Grose 2014 ³⁸ ; O'Brien 2011 ⁴⁷ ;	-	-	Bell 2021 ³ ; Morris 2022 ⁴⁰ ;	-	-

		Muir 2016 ⁸ ; Vallortigara 2023 ⁵⁴	Simpson 2018 ¹⁰ ; Specialist Healthcare Alliance 2023 ⁷⁷ ; Spencer-Tansley 2018 ⁴³			Khair 2019 ⁶³ ; Skirton 2010 ⁴⁸		
M34	Lack of knowledge	Cambridge 2016 ⁷⁸	-	-	Cambridge 2016 ⁷⁸	-	-	-
M35	Lack of information	Rodger 2015 ^{79**}	-	-	Cambridge 2016 ⁷⁸ ; Kahir 2019 ⁶³	-	Kahir 2019 ⁶³	-
O13	Variable care standards (focus is within RD community)	Cambridge 2016 ⁷⁸ ; Rodger 2015 ⁷⁹	-	-	Cambridge 2016 ⁷⁸ ; Kahir 2019 ⁶³	-	-	-
C18: End of life care								
M36	Lack of information	Whitehead 2012 ⁷³	-	-	-	-	-	-

Abbreviations: RD=rare disease; SES=socioeconomic status; SWAN=syndrome without a name

*Evidence from non-UK source (systematic review with international evidence)

**People who can't access specialist centres are less satisfied with information provision than those who can access specialist centres.

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